

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 4.1 Disseminate reports

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	4
1.1	List of reports and recommendations sent to Member States	4
1.2	Reports and recommendations sent to Member States	4
1.2.1	ZEP/CCUS SET Plan report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS and CCU projects.....	4
1.2.2	CCSA/ZEP report ‘Achieving a European market for CO2 transport by ship’	4
1.2.3	Call for concrete demand and supply side initiatives to promote a market for low-carbon products in the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy	5
1.2.4	ZEP statement on the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform proposal.....	5
1.2.5	EU Net-Zero Industry Act.....	5
1.2.6	Open letter on Article 18	6
1.2.7	Open letter ‘Harnessing the IPCEI mechanism to boost CCS and CCU’	6
1.2.8	Funding requirements for industrial carbon management deployment	6
1.2.9	ZEP’s response to the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy	7
1.2.10	‘Scaling up storage: mapping Europe’s CO2 storage sites’ (see also deliverable 3.1) ...	7
1.2.11	Public Perception: Key Enablers and Hurdles for CCS and CCU Projects	8
1.2.12	‘Certifying High-Quality Permanent Carbon Removals’	8
1.2.13	Government Group Meeting and Site Visits in Dunkirk	9
1.2.14	4th ICM Forum.....	9
1.2.15	Open Letter to Commission President calling for an Action Plan on industrial carbon management.....	9
2	ANNEX A: SUPPORTING DOCUMENTS.....	10

1 INTRODUCTION

This report is an overview of the efforts undertaken to disseminate ZEP reports and recommendations to Member State representatives between November 2023 and November 2024.

This is the second installment of the deliverable. The first version was delivered in August 2023.

1.1 List of reports and recommendations sent to Member States

ZEP regularly produces reports and position papers that are shared with Member States representatives.

Further details can be found in 1.2.

1.2 Reports and recommendations sent to Member States

1.2.1 ZEP/CCUS SET Plan report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS and CCU projects

Public perception is a key parameter for the deployment of CCS and CCU in Europe. Negative public perception can lead to policy decisions that would stop CCS and CCU projects or required policies. Positive public perception can stimulate the support of policymakers and accelerate project deployment. This report aims to synthesise findings on public perception related to CCS and CCU and provide key findings. These recommendations are crucial for policymakers that are developing their CCS and CCU policies and are looking for guidance on public perception management.

This report was developed by the secretariat and disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- a dedicated webinar (link to the [event](#));
- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#));
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the [publication](#) and below); and
- a dedicated presentation at the IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Council in June 2024 *see Annex A – Presentation public perception report AC79*).

1.2.2 CCSA/ZEP report ‘Achieving a European market for CO2 transport by ship’

In January 2024, ZEP together with CCSA published a report on the scope, enablers and barriers of CO2 transport by ship, outlining a series of policy and technical recommendations destined for policymakers. The report was officially launched through the webinar “Charting the Course for CCS”, hosted on 9 January by ZEP and CCSA, where multiple industry leaders and policymakers participated in a panel discussion on the enablers and barriers to achieving a market for CO2 transport by ship. Both the report and the webinar were promoted on ZEP’s LinkedIn account, and the webinar recording is available on CCSA’s Youtube account.

- ZEP-CCSA Report “Achieving a European market for CO2 transport by ship” ([Link to website publication](#))
- LinkedIn publication promoting the report ([Link to post](#))
- LinkedIn post promoting the webinar ([Link to post](#))
- Webinar recording ([Link to CCSA Youtube](#))

1.2.3 Call for concrete demand and supply side initiatives to promote a market for low-carbon products in the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy

ZEP co-signed an open letter calling on the European Commission to include policy initiatives to foster a market for low-carbon products on 1 February 2024. This letter was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#)); and
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the [publication](#) and below).

1.2.4 ZEP statement on the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform proposal

ZEP published a statement on 29 January 2024 to support the European Commission proposal for a regulation Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform that would have increased the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe programmes. This statement was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- Direct emails
- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#))
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the [publication](#))

1.2.5 EU Net-Zero Industry Act

ZEP shared its position on the proposal for a regulation Net-Zero Industry Act during the legislative process with Member State representatives. This statement was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- direct emails informing about ZEP's position
- the ZEP website (link to the webpages [here](#) and [here](#))

Direct emails included ZEP's position on elements of the proposed regulation. Those were sent to Member State representatives during the legislative process (*see Annex A – 'ZEP position - NZIA trilogues'*).

ZEP put forward amendments to the proposal for a regulation Net-Zero Industry Act before the vote of the European Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE) (link to the [amendments](#)).

Report 'Achieving a European market for CO₂ transport by ship'

ZEP developed, together with the Carbon Capture & Storage Association, the report 'Achieving a European market for CO₂ transport by ship' on 9 January 2024. This report was the result of a 1-year workstream aimed at gathering key policy, technical, and commercial findings on the role of shipping for CCUS and wider industrial decarbonisation. This report plays a key role for Member States and recommends national policy support for the transport of CO₂ by ship. Key areas of Member State cooperation are highlighted, including on cross-border transport and the London Protocol.

This open letter was a key position that was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- direct emails sent to Member State representatives;
- a dedicated webinar (link to the [event](#));
- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#));

- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the publications [here](#) and [here](#) and below); and
- the Government Group in October 2023 (see *Annex A – Government Group presentation and agenda*).

1.2.6 Open letter on Article 18

A critical element for CCS and CCU in the proposal for a regulation Net-Zero Industry Act was then-Article 18. ZEP's secretariat drafted, together with other signatories, the open letter 'Strong support for an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act Article 18 – solutions to make CCS work'. This open letter was a key position that was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- direct emails sent to Member State representatives;
- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#));
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (see publication below); and
- the Government Group in October 2023 (see *Annex A – Government Group presentation and agenda*).

1.2.7 Open letter 'Harnessing the IPCEI mechanism to boost CCS and CCU'

In June 2024, ZEP drafted and co-ordinated an open letter calling for an Important Project of Common European Interest for industrial carbon management. 30 members of the industrial carbon management community and several umbrella organisations co-signed this letter. The letter called on Member States' representatives of the Joint Forum for IPCEI (JEF-IPCEI) to prioritise ICM in the upcoming technical meeting and to increase the JEF-IPCEI effectiveness to allow for the rapid decarbonisation of hard-to-abate sectors. This statement was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- direct emails;
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the [publication](#) and below); and
- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#)).

Following this initiative, ZEP was invited to presented to the JEF-IPCEI clean tech working group, co-ordinated by Austria, where the ZEP Secretary General made a 60-minute presentation (including Q&A) to member state representatives and representatives from DG COMP. Following this presentation, members of the JEF-IPCEI have been invited to show support this initiative with a high-level meeting of the JEF scheduled for November 2024, outlining the work programme for 2025. There is considerable support for this initiative from Member States and it is anticipated that a pre-assessment of an IPCEI for industrial carbon management is likely to form part of the work programme for 2025.

The letter and the slides presented to the JEF-IPCEI are appended to this report.

1.2.8 Funding requirements for industrial carbon management deployment

The rapid deployment of industrial carbon management (ICM) at scale is required to reach the EU injection capacity objective of at least 50 million tonnes of CO₂ per annum by 2030. ZEP produced policy recommendations to Member States highlighting the crucial importance of increasing funding available for CCS in order to reach this objective. Some recommendations focus on elements of EU policy, such as the Connecting Europe Facility, while others focus on national elements, such as the need for increased

and more widespread national subsidy schemes. This statement was disseminated to Member State representatives via the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#)).

1.2.9 ZEP's response to the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy

The European Commission published its Communication 'Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU' on 6 February 2024. ZEP had been asking EU policymakers for a strategy dedicated to CCUS for years. Due to the importance of the strategy for Member States and the deployment of CCUS across Europe, ZEP published a dedicated response highlighting its position on the various elements and upcoming policies included in the strategy. This position was disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- the ZEP website (link to the [webpage](#))
- the ZEP LinkedIn account (link to the [publication](#) and screenshot below)

1.2.10 'Scaling up storage: mapping Europe's CO2 storage sites' (see also deliverable 3.1)

This webinar took place on 24 May 2024 on Microsoft Teams. It is the most attended meeting organised by ZEP under the grant period. 355 participants attended this webinar that aimed at *"ensuring accurate communication about CO2 storage capacity estimates and the status of ongoing and planned storage projects, crucial for the timely creation of the EU CO2 storage atlas"*. The targeted audience was EU and national officials with two objectives:

- communicating to EU and national public officials the difference between theoretical and available storage capacity; and
- underlining the efforts required to develop the storage sites necessary to meet the 2030 injection capacity objective under the EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act.

29 European public officials attended this webinar:

1. Svante Söderholm, Swedish Energy Agency
2. Kamila Paquel, European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change
3. Daniel Kitscha European Commission
4. Nicholas Young, Scottish Government
5. Adrian Lefvert, Swedish Energy Agency
6. Cassian Mariner-Edwards, UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero
7. Nicki Carnbrand Håkansson, Swedish Energy Agency
8. Hanne Siikavirta, Finnish Ministry of the Environment
9. Verena Falb, Agency for Energy and Climate Protection in North Rhine-Westphalia
10. Jeppe Sabroe Teghen, Danish Energy Agency
11. Helga Jónsdóttir, Icelandic Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Climate
12. Viana Ancu, UK North Sea Transition Authority
13. John Hughes, Scottish Government
14. Asa Söderlund, Swedish Energy Agency
15. Nick Richardson, UK North Sea Transition Authority
16. Stig Svenningsen, Norwegian Ministry of Energy
17. Christian Heller, German Ministry of the Environment
18. Meric Bulak, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development

19. Steven Vandenborre, Belgian Ministry of Health
20. Jo Bagguley, UK North Sea Transition Authority
21. Maria Velkova, European Commission
22. Alexander Engh, Norwegian Ministry of Energy
23. Michiel Martens, Flemish Energy and Climate Agency
24. Guillermo Martinez Castilla, European Commission
25. Lauren Russell, UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero
26. Jonathan Vouillamoz, Swiss Federal Office of Energy
27. Charles Galea, Maltese Government
28. Wael Khatib, UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero
29. Lisa-Maria Lovold, Norwegian Ministry of Energy

This webinar and its key messages were also disseminated to Member State representatives via:

- a LinkedIn publication (link to the [publication](#));
- the ZEP website (link to the [dedicated webpage](#)); and
- the ZEP YouTube channel (link to the [video](#)).

1.2.11 Public Perception: Key Enablers and Hurdles for CCS and CCU Projects

The ZEP Secretariat hosted this webinar on 20 June 2024 online. By sharing best practices, barriers and recommendations on stakeholder management for CCS projects, the webinar aimed to “*provide participants with practical insights and best practices on fostering public support for CCS initiatives*”. The webinar was attended by CCUS project developers, EU officials, national government representatives, emitters, industries, environmental NGOs and trade unions, and reached an attendance of 109 participants.

A report followed, published on 4 July 2024 on ZEP’s website, building from the CCUS Forum Working Group on Public Perception of CCUS’ six key considerations. The paper was disseminated through social media after its publication.

- LinkedIn promotion of the webinar ([Link here](#));
- Webinar recording, available in ZEP’s Youtube and extranet ([Link here](#));
- «Public Perception: Key Enablers and Hurdles for CCS and CCU Projects» published on ZEP’s website ([Link here](#));
- LinkedIn post sharing the publication of the paper ([Link here](#)).

1.2.12 ‘Certifying High-Quality Permanent Carbon Removals’

On 7 October 2024, ZEP published a series of Recommendations on Carbon Removal Certification methodologies. Supporting the adoption of the EC’s Carbon Removal and Carbon Framing Regulation, the report provides suggested additions to refine the newly adopted regulation. The report was launched via the webinar ‘Certifying High-Quality Permanent Carbon Removals: Key recommendations for permanent carbon removal methodologies’. The webinar gathered 129 attendees and included a panel discussion featuring representatives from DG CLIMA (Fabien Ramos), Bellona (Allanah Paul), SINTEF (Kristin Jordal) and Oxy (Ryan Edwards), following the presentation of the report.

Both the paper and webinar were promoted via ZEP's LinkedIn and website. Additionally, the webinar's recording is available on ZEP's Youtube and extranet.

The report was also referenced in the 5th meeting of the [Carbon Removal Expert Group](#) (which included various national representatives in attendance) in October 2024 in various remarks and questions raised by ZEP representative, Kristin Jordal.

- LinkedIn promotion of the webinar ([Link here](#));
- Webinar recording, available in ZEP's Youtube and extranet ([Link here](#));
- «Recommendations: Carbon Removal Certification Methodologies» published on ZEP's website ([Link here](#));
- LinkedIn post sharing the publication of the paper ([Link here](#)).

1.2.13 Government Group Meeting and Site Visits in Dunkirk

On 26-27 September 2024, ZEP's Government Group convened in person in Dunkirk, France, following site visits to Dunquerque LNG Terminal and ArcelorMittal Steel Plant where CO₂ transport and capture projects are underway. The meeting was attended in person by government representatives from Lithuania, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland, Belgium, France, as well as a representative from the European Commission and a member of the Global CCS Institute's team.

The meeting and visits presented an opportunity for government representatives working on ICM management to gather insights and see the logistics of developing and managing CCS projects. (See *Annex A- ZEP Government Group Visit to Dunkirk Practical Information*)

1.2.14 4th ICM Forum

In October, ZEP was represented at the [4th ICM Forum](#) in Pau, France, hosted by the French Government, by the ZEP Secretary General who moderated a panel on CO₂ standards. At the event, ZEP and CCS Europe organised a side event '[How to make CCS Happen](#)' which featured a presentation by ZEP, followed by a panel discussion including representatives from DG CLIMA (Maria Velkova), EPG (Luciana Miu), Oceos (Fred Lockwood) and CCS Europe (Chris Davies). The event was attended in person by various national representatives and other stakeholders in the industrial carbon management community.

- LinkedIn Post ([Link here](#))

1.2.15 Open Letter to Commission President calling for an Action Plan on industrial carbon management

In collaboration with CCS Europe, ZEP coordinated an open letter addressed to EC President Ursula Von Der Leyen and signed by 51 European CEOs and top executives calling for an EU Action Plan on industrial carbon management. A press release of the letter was published on ZEP's and CCS Europe's websites, as well as shared on LinkedIn.

- ZEP's Website Press Release ([Link here](#));
- LinkedIn post promoting the open letter ([Link here](#)).

2 ANNEX A: SUPPORTING DOCUMENTS

6. Updates from the External Relations Committee

Deliverable 2.4: Report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS/CCU projects focus on public perception

Key considerations:

1. Awareness and knowledge
2. Understanding the socio-demographic factors
3. Trust in the messenger and the project
4. Local involvement and empowerment of communities
5. Methods and channels of communication
6. Research on public perception

Case studies:

- Denmark
- Norway
- The Netherlands
- Spain
- France
- Poland

Objectives:

- Underscore the significance of public perception in the success of CCS projects.
- Recognise the gap in public awareness about CCS.
- Facilitate discussions among stakeholders about the relevance of public perception for CCS project development and deployment.

Target audience: ICM stakeholders, EU/national policymakers, project developers, research communities

ZEP STANCE ON THE POSITIONS AND DRAFT POSITION¹ OF THE THREE INSTITUTIONS ON THE NET ZERO INDUSTRY ACT

TOPICS	EUROPEAN COMMISSION	EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT	COUNCIL ²	ZEP STANCE
<p>Net zero technologies</p>	<p>net-zero technologies' means renewable energy technologies; electricity and heat storage technologies; heat pumps; grid technologies; renewable fuels of non-biological origin technologies; sustainable alternative fuels technologies; electrolysers and fuel cells; advanced technologies to produce energy from nuclear processes with minimal waste from the fuel cycle, small modular reactors, and related best-in-class fuels; carbon capture, utilisation, and storage technologies; and energy-system related energy efficiency technologies. They refer to the final products, specific components and specific machinery primarily used for the production of those products. They shall</p>	<p>(d) carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), removal, capture, transport, injection (EPP), storage and utilisation technologies;</p>	<p>CO₂ transport and carbon capture, utilisation, and storage technologies;</p>	<p>ZEP supports the Council text. The focus on CO₂ and the inclusion of the full value chain appears adequate.</p> <p>ZEP would like to add that carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies represent readily available and cost-efficient pathways for the decarbonisation of industrial and energy sectors in the EU. Some applications of carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) – where CO₂ is stored in a manner intended to be permanent – can also contribute to this goal.</p>

¹ The final Council position on the Net Zero Industry Act is not published as of 6 December 2023.

² Ibid.

	have reached a technology readiness level of at least 8.			
Net-zero strategic projects	<p>Member States shall recognise as net-zero strategic projects CO2 storage projects that meet the following cumulative criteria:</p> <p>(a) the CO2 storage site is located in the territory of the Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS);</p> <p>(b) the CO2 storage project contributes to reaching the objective set out in Article 18;</p> <p>(c) the CO2 storage project has applied for a permit for the safe and permanent geological storage of CO2 in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p>	<p>Member States shall recognise the following as net-zero strategic projects CO2 strategic projects:</p> <p>(a) the CO2 capture projects and the CO2 infrastructure projects necessary for the transport of captured CO2 to CO2 storage sites that: (i) meet the conditions laid down in Article 18(6), point (a); and (ii) aim to capture CO2 with the aim of storing it in a CO2 storage site as referred to in Article 16(1);</p> <p>(b) the CO2 storage projects that: (i) relate to CO2 storage sites located in the territory of the Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea; (ii) contribute to reaching the objective set out in Article 18; and (iii) have applied for a permit for the safe and permanent geological storage of CO2 in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p>	<p>Member States shall recognise as net-zero strategic projects CO2 storage projects that meet the following cumulative criteria:</p> <p>(a) the CO2 storage site is located in the territory of the Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS);</p> <p>(b) the CO2 storage project contributes to reaching the objective set out in Article 16;</p> <p>(c) the CO2 storage project has applied for a permit for the safe and permanent geological storage of CO2 in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p> <p>2a. CO2 capture projects and CO2 transport infrastructure projects that facilitate connections of installations capturing CO2 with CO2 storage sites recognised as net-zero strategic projects</p>	<p>ZEP supports the Council text. The full CCS value chain should be eligible for 'net-zero strategic projects' status.</p>

			according to paragraph 2, can also be considered as net-zero strategic projects	
Duration of the permit-granting process for net-zero strategic projects	<p>The permit-granting process for net-zero strategic projects shall not exceed any of the following time limits:</p> <p>(a) 9 months for the construction of net-zero strategic projects with a yearly manufacturing capacity of less than 1 GW;</p> <p>(b) 12 months for the construction of net-zero strategic projects, with a yearly manufacturing capacity of more than 1 GW;</p> <p>(c) 18 months for all necessary permits to operate a storage site in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p> <p>2. For net-zero strategic technologies for which a yearly manufacturing capacity is not measured in GW, the permit-granting process shall not exceed a time limit of 12 months.</p>	<p>The permit-granting process for net-zero strategic projects shall not exceed any of the following time limits:</p> <p>(a) six months for the construction of net-zero strategic projects with a yearly manufacturing capacity of less than 1 GW;</p> <p>(b) nine months for the construction of net-zero strategic projects, with a yearly manufacturing capacity of more than 1 GW;</p> <p>(c) 18 months for all necessary permits to operate a storage site in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p> <p>2. For net-zero strategic technologies for which a yearly manufacturing capacity is not measured in GW, the permit-granting process shall not exceed a time limit of nine months.</p>	<p>The permit-granting process for net-zero strategic projects shall not exceed any of the following time limits:</p> <p>(a) 9 months for the construction or expansion of net-zero strategic projects with a yearly manufacturing capacity of less than 1 GW;</p> <p>(b) 12 months for the construction or expansion of net-zero strategic projects, with a yearly manufacturing capacity of 1 GW or more;</p> <p>(c) 18 months for all necessary permits to operate a storage site in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC.</p> <p>2. For net-zero strategic technologies for which a yearly manufacturing capacity is not measured in GW, the permit-granting process shall not exceed a time limit of 12 months.</p>	<p>ZEP supports the European Commission and Council texts. A time limit of 12 months for net-zero strategic technologies for which a yearly manufacturing capacity is not measured in GW appears adequate.</p>

<p>Financing of net-zero technologies</p>	<p>/</p>	<p>1. Without prejudice to Directive 2003/87/EC, Member States shall report annually on the percentage of national revenues generated from the auctioning of the allowances, in accordance with the activities allowed under Article 10(3) of that Directive, that is used to support the objectives of this Regulation with a view of reaching at least 25%.</p> <p>2.</p> <p>3. 2. In accordance with Article 2 of [STEP Regulation] Net-Zero Strategic Projects selected pursuant to Article 10(1), points (a) or (b), of this Regulation are recognised as fulfilling the STEP objectives and shall therefore be eligible to receive the Sovereignty Seal under Article 4 of that Regulation as well as to receive funds in accordance with Article 9 of that Regulation.</p>	<p>/</p>	<p>ZEP supports the European Parliament text.</p> <p>ZEP supports the focus on low-income countries under the STEP regulation but would like to highlight that most planned CCS projects have a cross-border dimension. Clarification would be required regarding the eligibility of CCS projects aiming to capture CO₂ in EU countries with a GDP per capita below the EU average and transport the CO₂ for storage in other European countries.</p>
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<p>Union level objective of CO2 injection capacity</p>	<p>An annual injection capacity of at least 50 million tonnes of CO2 shall be achieved by 2030, in storage sites located in the territory of the European Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and which are not combined with Enhanced Hydrocarbon Recovery (EHR).</p>	<p>An annual injection capacity of at least 50 million tonnes of CO2 shall be achieved by 2030, in storage sites, meaning geological storage sites permitted under Directive 2009/31/EC including depleted oil and gas fields and saline aquifers, located in the territory of the Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea and which are not combined with Enhanced Hydrocarbon Recovery (EHR).</p> <p>2. The storage sites referred to in paragraph 1 shall be designed to operate for a minimum of five years.</p> <p>3. By 31 December 2026, the Commission shall propose, if appropriate, to the European Parliament and Council requirements for the annual CO2 injection capacity to be provided by 2035, 2040 and 2050, paying regard to the needs of Member States across the Union.</p>	<p>An annual injection capacity of at least 50 million tonnes of CO2 shall be achieved by 2030, in storage sites located in the territory of the European Union, its exclusive economic zones or on its continental shelf within the meaning of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and which are not combined with Enhanced Hydrocarbon Recovery (EHR).</p> <p>2. All storage sites shall be designed to operate for a minimum of five years and shall respect the principles of third-party access, non-discriminatory tariffs and transparency, as defined in Directive 2009/31/EC.</p>	<p>ZEP supports paragraphs 1, 2, and 4 of the European Parliament text. The inclusion of depleted oil and gas fields and saline aquifers in the description is a useful addition.</p> <p>ZEP supports the signature of agreements with neighbouring countries to achieve a Europe-wide market for CO₂ storage. The development of a strong CO₂ storage capacity by these neighbouring countries is crucial to achieve that market. Agreements related to CO₂ storage directive could be underpinned by the CO₂ storage directive or equivalent in the case of third countries located outside of the EU and the European Economic Area (EEA).</p>
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		<p>4. By ... [two years from the date of entry into force of this Regulation] and every two years thereafter, the Commission shall submit a report to the European Parliament and to the Council on the progress achieved towards the Union annual injection capacity target, including the state of the market related to the injection capacity. The report shall include an overview of the geographical spread of storage sites across the Union.</p> <p>5. The report referred to in paragraph 4 shall include a CO₂ storage and injection capacity adequacy assessment, using, in particular, the information collected pursuant to Article 17(2) and to Article 18 (6), which shall:</p> <p>(a) provide a detailed analysis of the geographical and temporal adequacies between the existing and planned CO₂ storage sites and the CO₂ capture projects for CO₂ emissions from industrial installations within the Union; (b) identify the main infrastructure needed for the transportation and storage of CO₂ emissions from</p>		
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		<p>industrial installations throughout the Union;</p> <p>(c) identify specific potential for CO2 usage to contribute to the permanent storage of CO2, which could lead to reduced needs for CO2 storage, or to reducing the Union's dependence on fossil fuels.</p> <p>6. Where the report referred to in paragraph 4 shows that the demand for CO2 injection capacity is significantly higher or lower than reflected in the capacity targets set out under paragraphs 1 and 3, the Commission shall adopt a delegated act in order to align the capacity targets with the demand.</p> <p>7. Where the report referred to in paragraph 4 of this Article shows that the market is insufficiently developed to provide an adequate injection capacity, the Commission may adjust the contributions under Article 18 while ensuring that the entities affected will have sufficient time to adjust their business plans to the newly defined obligations.</p>		
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		<p>8. The Union may integrate its neighbouring countries into its efforts under this Chapter by integrating the provisions of this Chapter in agreements with these countries or by establishing new agreements covering the provisions of this Chapter. When integrating these provisions in existing agreements or when establishing new agreements, the agreement shall ensure that all Union environmental, safety and security standards and requirements applicable for projects under this Chapter are respected in the third country. The agreement shall also set out an additional proportionate injection target for the third country as well as, in accordance with Article 18, a pro rata contribution for the relevant entities in the third country.</p>		
<p>Transparency of CO2 storage capacity data</p>	<p>By 3 months from the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall:</p> <p>(a) make publicly available data on areas where CO2 storage sites can be permitted on their territory.</p>	<p>By 3 months from the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall:</p> <p>(a) make publicly available data on areas where CO2 storage sites can be permitted on their territory.</p>	<p>By 6 months from the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall:</p> <p>(a) make data on all areas where CO2 storage sites could be permitted on their territory, including saline aquifers, publicly available, without</p>	<p>ZEP supports paragraphs 1a and 1c of the European Parliament text. The inclusion of saline aquifers in the description is useful.</p> <p>ZEP supports paragraph 2 and paragraph 2a of the European</p>

	<p>(b) oblige entities holding an authorisation as defined in Article 1, point 3, of Directive 94/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council⁷¹ on their territory to make publicly available all geological data relating to production sites that have been decommissioned or whose decommissioning has been notified to the competent authority.</p> <p>(c) For the purposes of point (a), the data shall include at least the information requested in the Commission Notice on the Guidance to Member States for the update of the 2021-2030 National Energy and Climate Plans.</p> <p>2. By six months from the entry into force of this Regulation and each year thereafter, each Member State shall submit to the Commission a report describing:</p> <p>(a) CO₂ capture projects in progress and an estimation of the corresponding needs for</p>	<p>(b) oblige entities holding an authorisation as defined in Article 1, point 3, of Directive 94/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on their territory to make publicly available on a non-reliance basis all raw geological data relating to production sites that have been decommissioned or whose decommissioning has been notified to the competent authority, and preliminary economic assessments of the respective costs of enabling CO₂ injection on each site, including data on:(i) whether the site is suitable for sustainably, safely and permanently injecting and storing CO₂; (ii) whether transport infrastructure and modes suitable for safely transporting CO₂ to reach the site is available or can be constructed..</p> <p>(c) For the purposes of point (a), the data shall include at least the information requested in the Commission Notice on the Guidance to Member States for the update of the 2021-2030 National Energy and Climate Plans and its subsequent updates.</p>	<p>prejudice to requirements regarding the protection of confidential information;</p> <p>(b) oblige entities which are or have been holders of an authorisation as defined in Article 1, point 3, of Directive 94/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council³⁵ on their territory to make publicly available all geological data relating to production sites that have been decommissioned or whose decommissioning has been notified to the competent authority, unless the entity has applied for an exploration permit in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC;</p> <p>(c) for the purposes of point (a), the data shall include at least the information requested in the Commission Notice on the Guidance to Member States for the update of the 2021-2030 National Energy and Climate Plans.</p>	<p>Parliament text. The description of efforts, including bilateral agreements, aimed at reaching the 50 million tonnes per annum injection capacity will be extremely useful.</p>
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	<p>injection and storage capacities;</p> <p>(b) CO₂ storage projects in progress on its territory, including the status of permitting under Directive 2009/31/EC, expected dates for Final Investment Decision (FID) and entry into operation;</p> <p>(c) the national support measures that could be adopted to prompt projects referred to in points (a) and (b).</p>	<p>2. By ... [six months from the date of entry into force of this Regulation] and each year thereafter, each Member State shall submit to the Commission a report, which shall be made publicly available, describing:</p> <p>(a) a mapping of CO₂ capture projects in progress on its territory or in cooperation with other Member States, and an estimation of the corresponding needs for injection and storage capacities, and CO₂ transport;</p> <p>(b) a mapping of CO₂ storage and CO₂ transport projects in progress on its territory, including the status of permitting under Directive 2009/31/EC, expected dates for Final Investment Decision (FID) and entry into operation;</p> <p>(c) the national support measures that have been adopted and measures that could be adopted to prompt projects referred to in points (a) and (b).</p>	<p>2. By six months from the entry into force of this Regulation and each year thereafter, each Member State shall submit to the Commission a report describing:</p> <p>(a) CO₂ capture projects in progress and an estimation of the corresponding needs and plans for transport, injection and storage capacities;</p> <p>(b) CO₂ transport and storage projects in progress on its territory, including the status of permitting under Directive 2009/31/EC, expected dates for Final Investment Decision (FID) and entry into operation;</p> <p>(c) the national support measures that have or will be adopted to prompt projects referred to in points (a) and (b), as well as measures relating to cross-border transportation of CO₂.</p> <p>3. Where no CO₂ storage projects are implemented in a Member State, it shall report on its plans to facilitate the</p>	
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		<p>(ca) the national strategy and targets that have been set for the capture of CO₂ by 2030, and when applicable in accordance with Article 16(3) for 2035, 2040 and 2050;</p> <p>(cb) the arrangements, including bilateral agreements made to facilitate cross-border transportation of CO₂, made to ensure that entities capturing CO₂ have access to a safe and non-discriminatory means of transporting CO₂;</p> <p>(cc) CO₂ transportation projects in progress and an estimation of the necessary future CO₂ transport projects' capacity to match the corresponding capture and storage capacity.</p> <p>2a. Should the report referred to in paragraph 2 show that no CO₂ storage projects are in progress on their territory, Member States shall report on plans to facilitate the decarbonisation of industrial sectors faced with unavoidable CO₂ emissions. This should include cross-border transport of CO₂ to storage sites located in</p>	<p>decarbonisation of industrial sectors or to develop cross-border transport of CO₂.</p>	
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		other Member States, as well as CO2 utilisation projects.		
CO2 transport infrastructure	/	<p>In order to facilitate the achievement of the objective set out in Article 16, the Union and its Member States in partnership with the companies benefiting shall ensure the needed investments in CO2 transport infrastructure, including cross-border infrastructure, are being made.</p> <p>2. Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that potential users of storage sites are able to obtain access to CO2 transport networks and to storage sites for the purposes of geological storage of the produced and captured CO2.</p> <p>3. In order to minimise the environmental impact of CO2 transport, the Union, its Member States and all other actors involved shall aim to minimise the need for CO2 transport.</p> <p>4. Member States may form, or may provide support for the</p>	/	ZEP supports the European Parliament text. Investments in CO ₂ transport infrastructure will be crucial to deploy CCS at scale.

		<p>formation of, entities that have the objective of creating CO2 transport networks including the construction of infrastructure or the provision of vessels or other means of conveyance. The formation of such entities shall be reviewed at least every two years.</p> <p>5. By ... [by six months from the date of entry into force of this Regulation], the Commission and Member States shall draw up a common strategy to finance the infrastructure referred to in paragraph 1.</p>		
Contribution to the injection capacity objective	<p>Each entity holding an authorisation as defined in Article 1, point 3, of Directive 94/22/EC shall be subject to an individual contribution to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity set in Article 16. Those individual contributions shall be calculated pro-rata on the basis of each entity's share in the Union's crude oil and natural gas production from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023 and shall consist of CO2 injection capacity in a storage site permitted in accordance</p>	<p>Each entity selling crude oil, petroleum products or natural gas in the Union shall be subject to an individual and obligatory contribution to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity set in Article 16. Those individual contributions shall be calculated pro-rata on the basis of each entity's share in crude oil, petroleum products and natural gas sold in the Union from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023 and shall consist of CO2 injection capacity in a storage site permitted in accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC on the</p>	<p>Each entity holding an authorisation as defined in Article 1, point 3, of Directive 94/22/EC shall be subject to an individual contribution to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity set in Article 16. Those individual contributions shall be calculated pro-rata on the basis of each entity's share in the Union's crude oil and natural gas production from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023 and shall consist of CO2 injection capacity in a storage site permitted in accordance</p>	<p>ZEP finds the European Parliament approach of setting an obligation on 'entities selling crude oil, petroleum products or natural gas in the Union' unworkable due to the very large number of actors falling under that category.</p>

	<p>with Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and available to the market by 2030. 2. Within three months of the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall, identify and report to the European Commission the entities referred to in paragraph 1 and their volumes in crude oil and natural gas production from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023. 3. Following the receipt of the reports submitted pursuant to Article 17 (2), the Commission after having consulted Member States and interested parties, shall specify the share of the contribution to the Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030 from entities referred to in paragraph 1. 4. Within twelve months of the entry into force of the Regulation, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall submit to the Commission a plan detailing how they intend to meet their contribution to Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030. Those plans shall: (a) confirm the entity's</p>	<p>geological storage of carbon dioxide and available to the market by 2030. 1a. Entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall be able to meet their individual contribution to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity through making available injection capacity in storages located in countries referred to in Article 16(8). 1b. Member States shall take the necessary measures to facilitate and incentivise emitters to capture emissions, to incentivise investors to finance the needed infrastructure to transport CO2 to the storage site, and where needed, to directly fund of CO2 storage projects. 1c. Where CO2 is captured and transported in one Member State and transported and stored in other Member States, Member States shall coordinate measures stated in paragraph 1b. The Commission shall ensure and facilitate such coordination through the establishment of CCS Regional Groupings. 2. Within three months of the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall, identify and report to the Commission the entities</p>	<p>with Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and available to the market by 2030. Entities with crude oil and natural gas production below a certain threshold as defined in accordance with a delegated act pursuant to paragraph 7 shall be excluded from this calculation and shall not be subject to a contribution. 2. Within three months of the entry into force of this Regulation, Member States shall, identify and report to the European Commission the entities referred to in paragraph 1 and their volumes in crude oil and natural gas production from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023. 3. Following the receipt of the reports submitted pursuant to Article 17 (2), the Commission after having consulted Member States and interested parties, shall specify the contributions to the Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030 from entities referred to in paragraph 1. 4. Within twelve months of the entry</p>	
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	<p>contribution, expressed in terms of targeted volume of new CO2 storage and injection capacity commissioned by 2030; (b) specify the means and the milestones for reaching the targeted volume.</p> <p>5. To meet their targeted volumes of available injection capacity, entities referred to in paragraph 1 can do any of the following: (a) develop CO2 storage projects alone or in co-operation; (b) enter into agreements with other entities referred to in paragraph 1; (c) enter into agreements with third party storage project developers or investors to fulfil their contribution.</p> <p>6. Two years after the entry into force of the Regulation and every year thereafter, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall submit a report to the Commission detailing their progress towards meeting their contribution. The Commission shall make these reports public.</p> <p>7. The Commission is empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 32 to</p>	<p>referred to in paragraph 1 and their volumes in crude oil and natural gas sale from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023.</p> <p>3. Following the receipt of the reports submitted pursuant to Article 17 (2), the Commission after having consulted Member States and interested parties, shall specify the share of the contribution to the Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030 from entities referred to in paragraph 1. Within twelve months of the entry into force of the Regulation, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall submit to the Commission a plan detailing how they intend to meet their contribution to Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030. Those plans shall: (a) confirm the entity's contribution, expressed in terms of targeted volume of new CO2 storage and injection capacity commissioned by 2030; (b) specify the means and the milestones for reaching the targeted volume.</p> <p>5. To meet their targeted volumes of available injection capacity, entities referred to in paragraph 1 can do any of the following: (a)</p>	<p>into force of the Regulation, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall submit to the Commission a plan detailing how they intend to meet their contribution to Union CO2 injection capacity objective by 2030. Those plans shall: (a) confirm the entity's contribution, expressed in terms of targeted volume of new CO2 storage and injection capacity commissioned by 2030; (b) specify the means and the milestones for reaching the targeted volume</p> <p>To meet their targeted volumes of available injection capacity, entities referred to in paragraph 1 can do any of the following: (a) develop CO2 storage projects alone or in co-operation; (b) enter into agreements with other entities referred to in paragraph 1; (c) enter into agreements with third party storage project developers or investors to fulfil their contribution.</p> <p>6. Two years after the entry into force of the Regulation and every year thereafter, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall</p>	
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	<p>supplement this Regulation concerning: (a) The modalities in which agreements between entities referred to in paragraph 1 and investments in storage capacity held by third parties are taken into account to meet their individual contribution under paragraph 5, points b and c. (b) The content of the reports referred to in paragraph 6.</p>	<p>invest in, or develop, CO2 storage projects alone or in co-operation; (b) enter into agreements with other entities referred to in paragraph 1, thereby considering the overall aim of increasing regional storage capacity across the Union; (c) enter into agreements with third party storage, capture and transport, project developers or investors to fulfil their contribution. 6. By ... [two years from the entry into force of the Regulation] and every year thereafter, the entities referred to in paragraph 1 shall submit a report to the competent authorities of the Members States and the Commission detailing their progress towards meeting their contribution. In accordance with Directive 2009/31/EC, that report shall include details on the newly commissioned storage capacities, the extent of its utilisation, and an overview of the economic feasibility of planned injection capacities and recommendations to the Member States on additional measured required to reach the CO2 injection targets. The Commission shall make these reports public.</p>	<p>submit a report to the Commission detailing their progress towards meeting their contribution. The Commission shall make these reports public. 6a. By derogation, a Member State may request the Commission to exempt the entities referred to in paragraph 1 from individual contribution in relation to the production activities they have carried out on the territory of that Member State from 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2023, provided that: (a) the overall annual injection capacity of all storage sites operated by any industry having received a storage permit within the meaning of Directive 2009/31/EC and having reached a final investment decision located on the territory of the Member State exceeds the sum of the individual contributions of the entities referred to in paragraph 1 in relation to the relevant production activities. The annual injection capacities associated with these storage</p>	
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		<p>6a. The Commission shall assess the compliance of the entities referred to in paragraph 1 with the requirements of this Chapter.</p> <p>In this assessment the Commission shall take into account the development of CO2 transport modalities to the injection sites as well as the development of CO2 capture activities to produce the demand for CO2 injection. If either or both infrastructure and capture activities, needed for a specific injection project to become operational, are lacking resulting in a specific entity not meeting its obligations this Article the Commission may reduce the injection obligation of a specific entity for a specific year. Any reduction shall be recovered within five years after the reduction took place. 7. The Commission is empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 32 to supplement this Regulation concerning: (a) The modalities in which agreements between entities referred to in paragraph 1 and investments in storage capacity held by third parties are</p>	<p>sites shall correspond to those mentioned in the storage permits and in the final investment decisions and contribute to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity set in Article 16.</p> <p>(b) the application is submitted before the end of [2027]. Provided that the two above conditions are met, the Commission shall adopt a decision exempting the entities concerned, referred to in paragraph 1, from their individual contribution in relation to the production activities they have carried out on the territory of the Member State submitting the request. Exempted entities may enter into agreements in accordance with paragraph 5, points (b) and (c) only in respect of any injection capacity exceeding the individual contribution from which they are exempted and the sum of the individual contributions that has been exempted. One year after the exempting decision and every year thereafter, the Member</p>	
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		<p>taken into account to meet their individual contribution under paragraph 5, points b and c. (b) The content of the reports referred to in paragraph 6; (ba) Dissuasive and proportionate sanctions and penalties that may be applied to entities referred to in paragraph 1 that fail to comply with the requirements of this Regulation. 7b. To contribute to the Union CO2 injection capacity objective, entities referred to in paragraph 1 are entitled to account the CO2 injection capacity corresponding to the project shares owned by another shareholder involved in a storage project, in case that shareholder does not fall under the scope of paragraph 1.</p>	<p>State shall submit a report to the Commission detailing the progress of the exempted entities towards meeting their contribution to the Union-wide target for available CO2 injection capacity set in Article 16. The Commission shall make these reports public. 7. The Commission is empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 32 to supplement this Regulation concerning: (-a) The rules concerning the identification of entities subject to contribution in accordance with paragraph 1, including the threshold below which entities are exempt from contribution; (a) The modalities in which agreements between entities referred to in paragraph 1 and investments in storage capacity held by third parties are taken into account to meet their individual contribution under paragraph 5, points b and c; (b) The content of the reports referred to in paragraph 6.</p>	
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			The conditions under which the Commission may exempt entities from part of their individual contribution in accordance with paragraph 6a.	
Regulatory framework for the market for captured CO2	/	<p>By ... [six months from the date of entry into force of the Regulation], the Commission shall publish guidelines indicating the maximum appropriate levels of CO2 purity and of trace elements within the flow that is to be specified by an entity seeking to have a CO2 storage project confirmed as contributing to the Union's injection capacity objective.</p> <p>2. By ... [2 years from the date of entry into force of this Regulation], the Commission shall carry out an assessment in accordance with paragraph 2 and, if appropriate, submit a legislative proposal to establish a regulatory framework for a Union-wide CO2 capture, usage, storage and transport market to complement the rules set out in Directive 2009/31/EC, laying down rules on:</p>	/	ZEP supports the European Parliament provision, noting that sufficient time should be allocated to develop CO2 specifications. A regulatory framework for a Union-wide CO2 capture, usage, storage and transport market will support the development of CCS in Europe.

		<p>(a) open, fair and non-discriminatory access and safety of the CO2 storage and transport network;</p> <p>(b) open, fair and non-discriminatory access to capture CO2 for usage or storage purposes;</p> <p>(c) the functioning and interconnection of the CO2 transport network and other infrastructure across the Union;</p> <p>(d) economic incentives, funding and financial assistance mechanisms;</p> <p>(e) specification standards for CO2 storage and transport;</p> <p>(f) environmental standards;</p> <p>(g) guarantees for the origin of CO2;</p> <p>(h) enforcement mechanisms.</p> <p>2a. Before adopting any legislative proposal as referred to in paragraph 2, the Commission shall assess whether:</p>		
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		<p>(a) the functioning of the CO2 market ensures sufficient access to injection capacity for unavoidable CO2 emissions;</p> <p>(b) the obligations set out in Article 18(1) effectively promote the development of the CO2 storage market in the Union. Where the assessment pursuant to this paragraph shows that the market is not developing in line with the objectives of this Regulation, the Commission may decide to include rules to provide priority access for unavoidable emissions to injection capacity as well as to amend this Regulation to change the obligations set out in Article 18(1). The Commission shall ensure that all sectors with unavoidable industrial process emissions have sufficient access to the CO2 injection capacity. Where its assessments show the market is not developing in line with this objective, the Commission shall develop rules to provide priority access for unavoidable industrial process emissions to the CO2 injection capacity. To facilitate the</p>		
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		<p>assessment pursuant to this paragraph, the Commission shall develop a list of sectors with unavoidable industrial process emissions from large-scale industrial installations for which no direct emissions reduction options are available after the best available techniques have been applied, based on a clear methodology including scientific evidence, the current state-of-the-art of relevant technologies, economic feasibility, as well as appropriate demand-side emissions reduction measures.</p>		
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ZEP Government Group meeting

4 October 2023

Hybrid meeting

Draft agenda

Welcome and introduction	Secretariat	10:00 – 10:10
Updates from ZEP	Secretariat	10:10 – 10:20
Updates on national CCS/CCU developments	All	10:20 – 11:15
Net Zero Industry Act	Secretariat	11:15 – 11:45
National energy and climate plans	Secretariat	11:45 – 12:05
Industrial carbon management strategy	Secretariat	12:05 – 12:25
Next meeting dates and AOB	Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

Draft agenda

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Next meeting dates and AOB	Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

- Introduction of ZEP's new secretary-general Joop Hazenberg

Objectives

- De-risking projects
- Accelerating projects
- Enabling cost-effective realisation of projects

Approach

- Enable real **project-to-project knowledge sharing** on good practices and experiences;
- Address **on-the-ground enablers and barriers** encountered during projects;
- Recommend to the EC and governments **necessary policy/regulation, funding and business model actions.**

3 Co-Chairs

1. Permanent Co-chair: Stijn Santen (EBN)
2. Rotating Co-chair: Host Project
3. Representative from the European Commission

Organisation

- Every 4/6 months
- Organised in cooperation with and held on project side

Membership

- Open membership
- Project developers, Representatives from EU/National/Regional/Local Governments/Authorities, R&I Community

Meetings

- 2 days meetings
- Both open and closed sessions

Outcome

- Conclusions and Recommendations to be presented to ZEP government group and project developers

ZEP Projects Network

- First Projects Network Meeting in partnership with the Porthos Project in Rotterdam
- Date to be confirmed

Draft agenda

Welcome and introduction	Secretariat	10:00 – 10:10
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Next meeting dates and AOB	Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

State-of-play

- ENVI committee vote on 20 September
 - ‘do no significant harm’ criteria for net zero strategic technologies
 - priority to ‘unavoidable industrial process emissions’
 - annual injection capacity target of at least 60 million tonnes of CO₂, covering the EEA
 - ‘contribution of economic operators offering petroleum products, natural gas or coal on the Union market’
- ITRE committee vote on 25 October, plenary vote in October/November
- Council’s General Approach could be expected for December
- Trilogues could start in December

ZEP actions

- ZEP published its position on the Net Zero Industry Act
- ZEP sent proposed amendments for the draft ITRE report
- ZEP published an open letter for an implementable and pragmatic Article 18, together with Bellona, the Carbon Capture & Storage Association, the Clean Air Task Force, the International Association of Oil & Gas Producers, and SINTEF

What are your views on the Act?

Can the Act be finalised before the 2024 European Parliament election?

Draft agenda

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Industrial carbon management strategy	Secretariat	12:05 – 12:25
Next meeting dates and AOB	Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

State-of-play

- Ongoing update of the NECPs for 2021-2030
- European Commission guidance encourages information on CCS
- Draft plans not available yet:
 - Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Latvia, Malta, Poland, and Romania

What is the timeline for the publication of the final plans?

How is CCS and CCU currently reflected in the draft plans?

Draft agenda

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Next meeting dates and AOB	Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ZEP actions

- Longstanding policy request
- Response to the public consultation, EC workshop this Friday
- Request for the strategy to be published this year

CCUS Forum

- ZEP supported Forum working group on CO2 infrastructure and Forum expert group on CO2 specifications
- Both reports on the CCUS Forum website
- Plenary on 27-28 November in Aalborg, Denmark

ZEP actions

- Longstanding policy request
- Response to the public consultation, EC workshop this Friday
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- ZEP supported Forum working group on CO2 infrastructure and Forum expert group on CO2 specifications – both reports published
- Plenary on 27-28 November in Aalborg, Denmark

Which elements should be included in the upcoming EU strategy?

Draft agenda

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Next meeting dates and AOB

Meeting in Berlin on 14 November

- *Government Group meeting* 10:30-12:30 (Hannoversche Strasse 28-30, Berlin)
- *Lunch break* 12:30-14:00
- *Visit to the cement plant* 14:00-18:00

Can you raise your (virtual) hand to confirm in-person participation?

Next meeting dates and AOB

We are still looking for a chair!

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 4 October 2023, 10:00 – 12:30 CEST

Online meeting: Microsoft Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	ZEP secretariat	10:00 - 10:10
2 Updates from ZEP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New ZEP Secretary-General New Projects Network – presentation and coordination with the Government Group 	ZEP secretariat, All	10:10 – 10:20
3 Updates on national CCS and CCU developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roundtable – country updates Policy and funding developments Bilateral agreements 	All	10:20 – 11:15
4 Net Zero Industry Act <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative state-of-play – <i>pre-read 2</i> Group discussion: what are your views on the Act? can the Act be finalised before the 2024 European Parliament election? 	ZEP secretariat, All	11:15 – 11:45
5 National Energy and Climate Plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> State-of-play and next steps – <i>pre-read 3</i> How will CCS and CCU be included in the updated NECPs? 	ZEP secretariat, All	11:45 – 12:05
6 Industrial carbon management strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP's position – <i>pre-read 4</i> Group discussion: which elements are key for the strategy? 	ZEP secretariat, All	12:05 – 12:25
7 Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 14 November (Berlin) – <i>pre-read 5</i> 	ZEP secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ZEP Government Group visit to Dunkirk – Practical information

Day 1: 25 September	
12.00 – 12.30	Departure Group 1 from Dunkirk Train station to Dunkerque Terminal
13.00 – 13.30	Departure Group 2 from Dunkirk Train station to Dunkerque Terminal
14.00 – 17.00	Visit of Dunkerque LNG Terminal and future d'Artagnan project
17.00 – 17.15	Transport from Terminal to Dunkirk Centre
19.00	Dinner at Le Protocole
Day 2: 26 September	
08.30	Departure from IBIS Centre to Arcelor Mittal steel plant
09.00 – 12.00	Visit of Arcelor Mittal and presentation of DMX CO2 Capture Pilot
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch hosted by ArcelorMittal
13.00 – 13.15	Shuttle bus from ArcelorMittal
14.00 – 16.00	ZEP Government Group hybrid meeting at Dunkirk Townhall

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